

Urinary Bladder Echinococcosis Causing Cystitis, Hydatiduria and Bilateral Hydroureteronephrosis: A Rare Case Report

Preeti Tiwari ✉

Assistant professor, Department of Radiology, Maharani Laxmibai Medical College, Jhansi, India

Tushar Agrawal

Junior resident, Department of Radiology, Maharani Laxmibai Medical College, Jhansi, India

Jamil Akhter

Junior resident, Department of Radiology, Maharani Laxmibai Medical College, Jhansi, India

Vijay Kumar Sharma

Assistant professor, Department of General Surgery, Maharani Laxmibai Medical College, Jhansi, India

More Information

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Abstract

Hydatid disease or cystic echinococcosis is a parasitic zoonosis, caused by larval stages of *Echinococcus granulosus*. Hydatid cysts usually affect liver followed by lungs and less commonly spleen, kidney, heart and other organs. Hydatid cysts of urinary bladder is very rare with only few case reports published till now. In a systematic review of literature by Hasan et al., only 7 cases were found of urinary bladder hydatid cyst [1]. We are reporting a case of 65-year-old male, diagnosed to have urinary bladder hydatid cyst by radiological imaging and urine investigations.

Introduction

Hydatid cyst remains the differential diagnosis of cystic lesions in endemic areas. Although urinary tract involvement represents only 2-4% of all hydatid disease, kidneys remain the most common site [2,3]. Bladder [4] involvement is mostly by hematogenous route [5]. Cyst usually grows slowly and may persist for long time without symptoms. Patients may remain asymptomatic or may present with pyuria, dysuria, urgency, hydatiduria or acute retention of urine. Diagnosis is usually made by radiological imaging. Treatment is surgical excision after giving short course of albendazole [6]. In some cases where complete surgical excision is not feasible, marsupialisation of cysts with evacuation of all contents is a viable option [2].

Case Report

We are reporting a case of 65-year-old male, farmer by occupation presented with complaints of pyuria and suprapubic pain for 5 months. Patients also give history of dysuria, intermittent straining with passage of

membranes in urine. Patient was evaluated by routine blood investigations, urine microscopy, USG abdomen and CECT abdomen. USG abdomen (see Fig 1a, 1b) revealed a 72x62mm size large thick wall cystic lesion posterior to urinary bladder and showing free communication with the urinary bladder suggestive of bladder diverticula.

It is completely filled with multiple cysts, thick floating membranes and echoes showing typical cyst within cyst appearance suggestive of daughter cysts with hydatid sand. Similar finding is noted in urinary bladder. Urinary bladder wall is thickened and trabeculated with increased vascularity. There was associated bilateral moderate hydroureteronephrosis as a sequela to chronic cystitis. CECT abdomen revealed similar findings (see Fig 2a,b).

Urine microscopy showed pus cells, classic scolices and hooklets (Figure 3a,b). Patient was started on albendazole 400mg twice a day. Patient was lost to follow up so we don't have record of further treatment.

Figure 1a,b: USG Image

Figure 2a,b: CECT Image

Figure 3a,b: Microscopy Images of Scolices and Hooklets

Conclusion

Urinary bladder hydatid cyst is very rare and only few case reports are there till now. Radiographical techniques are better diagnostic tests of hydatid cyst than serological tests. Treatment options are medical, radiological and surgical depending on site and type of

hydatid cyst. In our case plan was to give albendazole for 2 weeks followed by surgical excision but patient lost to follow up. In post operative period patient should be followed closely because of chances of recurrence.

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References

- [1] Hasan RA, Abdullah F, Saeed BT. Hydatid cysts of the bladder: a systematic review of the literature. *Barw Med J.* 2023 Aug 23;1(3):21–24. doi:10.58742/bmj.v1i2.46
- [2] Deodhar SD, Patel VC, Kirloskar MS. Hydatid disease of urinary bladder (a case report). *J Postgrad Med.* 1986;32(1):46–48.
- [3] Cherkaoui MM, Nassar I, Jroundi L, et al. Hydatid disease of the urinary bladder: a case report. *J Radiol.* 2002;83:45–46.
- [4] Hertz M, Zissin R, Dresnik Z, Morag B, Itzhak Y, Jonas P. Echinococcus of the urinary tract: radiologic findings. *Urol Radiol.* 1984;6(3-4):175–181. doi:10.1007/BF02923719
- [5] Ganie FA, Dar OH, Kaleem A, et al. Hydatid cyst of urinary bladder. *Indian J Nephrol.* 2013;23:462–463. doi:10.4103/0971-4065.120348
- [6] Salehi A, Salehi H, Jenabi E. Pelvic hydatid cyst with hydroureteronephrosis: a rare case report. *Case Rep Infect Dis.* 2021;2021:1–4. doi:10.1155/2021/2090849

